

PERSONALITY OF PUBLISHERS ABOUT CRAFTSMAN IN STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7802869>

Abstract. *The article details the formation of skills in students as a result of their knowledge of crafts.*

Keywords: *craftsman, knowledge, ability, co 'skill, technology, school, profession, qualification, student, inclination, interest, service, design.*

At the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirzioev, the number of decisions, which were adopted for the benefit of artisans, the benefits created for artisans, the support of artisans and the interests of artisans increased sharply. After the focus on this craft, our people's interest in national crafts has increased. After all, it is one of the priorities of our country, our people to inculcate our national traditions, our national spiritual values in the minds of students, to teach them how to care, to increase their spiritual knowledge, to raise children who value the crafts of our ancestors. The search for cultural specimens of our people by archeologists, ethnographers, their transfer to museum funds has been intensified. It is the national moral duty of every citizen of Uzbekistan to preserve the continuity of the craft by studying and continuing the mysteries of national values. These tasks have led to the further development of handicrafts in Uzbekistan, laying the groundwork for the preservation of national values.

The requirements for training and their place in the orientation of students of secondary schools to the craft are of paramount importance. The content of the school curriculum determines the preparation of handicraft products and vocational interest, the inclusion of knowledge about professional development in the program plan.

It is a much to see the content of the technology curriculum in directing students to the craft. The main purpose of teaching technology in general secondary education is to apply the knowledge, skills and competencies gained by students in the technical and technological and technological operations in independent practical activities, career selection, formation of competencies for active access to social relations on the basis of national and universal values.

The main tasks of teaching technology in general secondary education are:

study of materials and their properties, properties, as well as information on technical objects and technological processes;

knowledge of special and general labor operations in the technical object and technological processes;

management of technological processes, practical application of special and general labor operations;

formation of technical and creative thinking, intellectual abilities;

ability to analyze the technological process and the sequence of execution of prepared products, as well as product quality;

to draw conclusions about the performance of goods and processes and to evaluate labor operations, product quality;

consists of the formation and development of competencies in the field of base and technology in the implementation of the work of consciously preparing for career choice.

In general, secondary schools, the science of technology is generalized with the field of primary education, in grades 5-9 “Technology and design”, “Service is taught in the direction of” [4].

The Department of Technology and Design for the 8th-9th grades of the National Crafts General Orta Education Schools will be taught in the field of public crafts technology. Assessment of products produced by the people's crafts for export and the domestic market, the appearance of handicrafts, the composition of the structure and integrity, compositional integrity, types of folk crafts in Uzbekistan, development history and prospects, organization of exhibitions and competitions in folk crafts and the rules of selection of participants, product preparation technologies are taught, and these topics serve as a basis for directing students to national crafts.

After students have mastered the topics given in the curriculum in the science of technology, it is important to direct students to the choice of profession, properly analyze their interests, desires, abilities. the problem is.

When students choose a profession, the fact that they are masters of their profession evaluates the fact that general secondary schools are properly organized to direct their careers.

To this end, the following work is a key issue in educational institutions, and the following is taken into account:

study of individual characteristics, interests, abilities and inclinations of students;

to provide relevant concepts to students on the basis of the current needs of career choice in society, inextricably linked with the socio-economic development of our country;

In order to take up the profession, students must be taken to secondary special educational institutions and higher education institutions of their chosen profession and introduced to the conditions of teaching. Interest, inclination and ability are the primary qualities in choosing a profession. The scientific name for behaviors that determine interests in an appropriate profession based on such qualities is called profdiagnostics. The term is derived from Greek, and its exact translation “professio” - my own training and “diagnostikos” - means to identify, notice or understand. The main purpose of profdiagnostics – is to identify a profession that is relevant to a person’s interests, abilities, and inclinations. Interest is understood as an active cognitive activity of a person focused on this or that subject. Interests in career choice are a person’s positive attitude towards a particular field of work, his or her desire to know and operate.

Interests vary depending on their content, scale, length, and depth. The content and scope of interests reflect a person’s level of knowledge and curiosity about everything. The depth and longevity of the interests show their stability.

Interests go through several stages in their development. At first, they are temporary, episodic in nature, and show a positive attitude towards a particular subject. If such interests are not developed, they will soon subside or disappear altogether. As this or that subject is studied in depth and on a regular basis, and carefully entered into an interesting area of labor activity, interests can become stronger, stronger, and gradually become a sustainable interest. Such interests often grow and grow and become Mayl [6.43-b.].

Miles is said to be a – person’s desire to engage in mueyan activities and to constantly improve their knowledge by improving skills and competencies appropriate to the type of sectarian activity.

Interest – plays a directly important role in people’s worldviews, ethics, ideals, i.e. its lofty goals, dreams, dreams, and serves to ensure their success. The classification of interests and their content are expressed in the table above. Curiosity helps to develop knowledge, conscious, thorough, stable, comprehensible, o ‘ pupil ability, mind, curiosities, a more perfect understanding of the world, an expansion of the level of knowledge.

Ability is such a psychological feature of a person that the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies depends on these characteristics. However, these features alone do not provide general o ‘ secondary school education for these knowledge and skills. an individual's abilities in terms of skills, abilities and knowledge are manifested in some way. Skills are opportunities and are a skill level in a job. The ability to show music in a child should include opportunities, special education, antiquity, good health, musical instruments, notes, and many other conditions for him to become a musician. If Miles does not show interest ‘, the abilities will not develop and will cause the tourist to die without progress.

Abilities are manifested only in activity. If the student is seriously examined on the grounds that he or she does not have the necessary skills and skills system and methods of finding solid knowledge, it is a serious psychological mistake for the educator to conclude that he or she does not have the skills in a hurry.

Ability is not reflected in knowledge and skills, but in the system of their acquisition, that is, how fast, in different conditions, in the process of mastering the knowledge and skills that are important for sectarian activity, appears to be light and durable in implementation [6. 46-b].

Table 1. Vocational guidance paradiagma for students.

B.E.According to Kadyrov, competence is called the ability to apply this knowledge in practice by those educated, forming a certain science or a complex of mastered knowledge [7].

Students also receive the use of spiritual, cultural values from the content of educational activities. Therefore, activities should be carried out based on psychological, pedagogical, didactic goals. The importance and possibility of educational activities for the future life of students, effective labor activities and the acquisition of the foundations of various professions is great.

When we analyze the technology of vocational guidance in the choice of professions of students, it is possible to gain interest in the profession even by giving students information about professions through the professionogram.

A professionogram is a short professional description that relies on the psychological characteristics of a person. This gives the following information. general information about the

profession, the type of profession, knowledge, skills and qualifications, important professional qualities, personal qualities, working conditions, work schedule, medical monelik(restrictions), consists of places where it is possible to work. The necessary component of the professiogram was the Occupational psychogram [5. 145 P.].

A psychogram is a psychological recommendation of professional activity, which determines the indicators of the psychophysiological and personal qualities of each worker. At the beginning of the 20th century, the psychogram was seen as the sum of the necessary qualities of the profession of a person. The term psychogram was coined by the German psychologist B. Recommended by Shtern [5. 147 P.].

It became known from the above that students have initial knowledge of the types of crafts, that they have the skill in these handicrafts by preparing a craft product, that the student relies on this knowledge, knowledge, skills and use in his home, unfamiliar situations general secondary education leads to the development and formation of interest, inclinations, abilities in the craft professions of schoolchildren. As a result, on the basis of the education and upbringing provided by the schools of general secondary education, our students become masters of craftsmanship, greatly contribute to the progressive development of society and take their place.

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